

Creep Mechanisms of a Two-Phase, A2-B2 Superalloy

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Abstract

1 The refractory element-based 27.3Ta-27.3Mo-27.3Ti-8Cr-10Al (at.%) high entropy alloy with a
2 precipitation-strengthened A2-B2 microstructure exhibits substantial B2 raft formation and a transition
3 in apparent creep exponent near 125 MPa at 1030 °C. This study reveals the 3D morphology of the
4 rafted B2 precipitates and establishes the stress-dependent dislocation mechanisms that govern creep.
5 Focused ion beam 3D reconstruction shows that rafted B2 precipitates exhibit an irregular, plate-like
6 geometry, characterized by elongation on two orthogonal faces and polygonality on the third, a
7 morphology that cannot be resolved by conventional 2D imaging. Transmission electron microscopy
8 (TEM) analyses reveal a shift in dislocation–precipitate interaction with increasing applied stress. At
9 low stresses, deformation is primarily governed by dislocation climb, whereas at high stresses, it is
10 dominated by cross slip of screw dislocations, resulting in a power-law breakdown. In the intermediate
11 regime, deformation is controlled by a climb-mediated mechanism coupled with cutting of the B2 phase
12 by strongly paired dislocations. High-resolution scanning TEM further confirms that the A2/B2
13 interfaces remain fully coherent across all creep conditions examined.

Keywords

14 A2-B2, Superalloys, Refractory High-Entropy Alloys, Creep Deformation, Dislocation-Precipitate
15 Interaction, 3D Microstructure

1. Introduction

16 Refractory high-entropy alloys (RHEAs) with body-centered cubic (BCC) crystal structures
17 (Strukturbericht designation A2) have attracted considerable attention as potential candidates for high-
18 temperature applications. Their exceptionally high solidus temperatures, reaching up to 2900 °C [1,2],
19 slow diffusion of the refractory elements [3,4], and strong solid-solution strengthening enable them to
20 retain remarkable strength even at elevated temperatures [1,2]. Representative alloys, such as
21 NbMoTaW, have been reported to exhibit outstanding compressive yield strength, for example,
22 approximately 405 MPa at 1600°C under quasi-static loading [1]. In contrast, the state-of-the-art Ni-
23 based superalloy CMSX-4 exhibits a yield strength of below 100 MPa at only 1200 °C [3,4]. This
24 remarkable high-temperature strength highlights their potential as next-generation structural materials,
25 particularly since Ni-based superalloys are fundamentally limited by their γ' solvus (~ 1280 °C, e.g., for
26 CMSX-4) and solidus temperature (~ 1350 °C) [5–7].

27 Despite their excellent high-temperature strength, single-phase BCC RHEAs exhibit inadequate creep
28 resistance. This limitation is exemplified by the equimolar (single-phase) A2 alloy TiZrHfNbTa, which
29 exhibits markedly lower creep resistance in the temperature range of 980-1100 °C compared to
30 precipitation-strengthened, single-crystal Ni-based superalloys, such as CMSX-4, or even the solid
31 solution matrix thereof [8,9]. Such limited creep performance can be attributed to a number of aspects,
32 like the polycrystalline nature of the alloy, the absence of precipitation strengthening, the higher
33 diffusivity associated with the open A2 crystal structure, and the microstructural instability arising from
34 the gradual decomposition of A2 into an A2 and hexagonal close packed (HCP, Strukturbericht
35 designation A3) phases during prolonged exposure [9]. In contrast, Ni-based superalloys achieve creep
36 resistance through their two-phase microstructure consisting of coherent and thermally stable ordered
37 $L1_2$ particles (γ') embedded in a face-centered cubic (FCC, Strukturbericht designation A1) matrix (γ),
38 which provides effective and sustained precipitation strengthening [7,10,11]. This highlights the critical
39 role of thermo-mechanically stable precipitates in maintaining creep resistance. Motivated by this
40 concept, recent studies have successfully introduced ordered B2 precipitates into forming
41 multicomponent two-phase A2-B2 alloys that combine solid-solution and precipitation strengthening
42 [12–30]. However, systematic investigations of their creep behavior and the governing mechanisms in
43 such two-phase systems remain scarce.

44 27.3Ta-27.3Mo-27.3Ti-8Cr-10Al (at.%, hereafter TMT-8Cr-10Al) represents a prototypical example,
45 consisting of an A2 matrix with coherent, ordered B2 precipitates. In our previous work [13,31], phase
46 separation was observed to occur upon cooling between 1060 and 1070 °C, followed by the ordering of
47 the precipitates at approximately 1055 °C. The resulting B2 phase exhibits excellent microstructural
48 stability even after prolonged exposure near the solvus temperature, which can be attributed to the high
49 solidus temperature and the intrinsically low diffusivity of the refractory elements [12,32]. Our recent
50 study showed that polycrystalline TMT-8Cr-10Al at 1030 °C ($\sim 0.98 T_s$) exhibits creep resistance
51 comparable to the single-crystal superalloy CMSX-4 tested at 1050 °C ($\sim 0.85 T_s$) at similar stress levels
52 [33,34]. Moreover, B2 precipitates in $\langle 100 \rangle$ -oriented grains rafted perpendicular to the compression
53 loading axis, consistent with the behavior reported for Co-based superalloys, which is associated with a

54 positive lattice misfit [35,36]. These findings highlight TMT-8Cr-10Al as a model system for exploring
55 the creep mechanisms of precipitation-strengthened RHEAs.

56 Mechanistic insights into RHEAs have so far been derived primarily from single-phase systems,
57 particularly BCC alloys such as TiZrHfNbTa and VNbMoTaW [37–39]. A strength plateau between
58 800 and 1200 °C in HfMoNbTaW (as observed in compression testing) is attributed to a shift from screw
59 to edge dislocation-dominated deformation [40]. In addition to these primary processes, secondary
60 mechanisms such as kink-band formation have been reported for room-temperature tensile deformation
61 in $Ti_{135}Zr_{(35-x)}Hf_xNb_{20}Mo_{10}$ alloys, which further redistribute strain and improve fracture resistance [41].
62 Liu et al. [8] have reported solute drag mechanisms in single-phase HfNbTaTiZr within the tensile creep
63 temperature range of 1100 to 1250 °C and a stress range of 5 to 30 MPa, where dislocations are randomly
64 distributed throughout the matrix and deformation is controlled by $1/2\langle 111 \rangle$ slip. In contrast, a recent
65 study on the tensile creep behavior of the Nb₄₅Ta₂₅Ti₁₅Hf₁₅ RHEA at 900 °C and stresses between 50-
66 300 MPa has reported an apparent stress exponent of 4.1 and has revealed that creep deformation is
67 controlled by cross-kink collisions from screw dislocations, leading to dipole drag at lower strain rate
68 and jog drag at higher strain rate [42]. By contrast, the B2 phase often acts as a strengthening phase in
69 high-temperature alloys. In binary B2 intermetallics, such as NiAl [30] and TiFe [31], the deformation
70 behavior has been systematically investigated, providing valuable insights into their slip systems and
71 strength anomaly phenomena [43–46]. In Al-containing RHEAs, however, the role of the B2 phase
72 becomes considerably more complex. In addition to its intrinsic stability, the strengthening efficiency
73 strongly depends on the antiphase boundary energy (APB) energy, which governs how dislocations
74 interact with ordered precipitates [47,48]. For the presently investigated TMT-8Cr-10Al alloy, the APB
75 energy was estimated to be (150 ± 39) mJ/m² [49].

76 Our previous work investigated the creep behavior of the TMT-8Cr-10Al alloy in the temperature range
77 of 1000-1060 °C at applied stresses of 75-175 MPa [31]. Two distinct regimes were identified, namely
78 a high creep resistance (HCR) regime at lower temperatures and a low creep resistance (LCR) regime
79 at higher temperatures. Temperatures at and above 1040 °C fall within the LCR regime, where the creep
80 strength decreases markedly due to partial dissolution of the B2 phase as the temperature approaches
81 the solvus temperature (1060-1070 °C), leading to a significant reduction in the B2 volume fraction [31].
82 In contrast, at or below 1030 °C in the HCR regime, the alloy exhibits superior creep resistance which
83 is comparable to that of single-crystalline CMSX-4 tested under similar conditions. However, the
84 interaction of dislocations at the A2-B2 interface remains unknown. In this study, we address this gap
85 with the two-phase RHEA TMT-8Cr-10Al. Samples crept at 1030 °C under applied stresses of 100, 125,
86 and 150 MPa were examined, with the 125 MPa condition marking a transition in creep exponent,
87 indicative of a shift in the dominant deformation mechanism. Therefore, three specific research
88 questions will guide this study:

- 89 (1) What is the 3D morphology of the rafted B2 precipitates after creep deformation?
- 90 (2) How do dislocation-precipitate interactions evolve with applied stress, and which mechanisms
91 become prevalent in each creep regime?
- 92 (3) How does the A2/B2 interface behave under creep, and does it retain atomic-scale coherency
93 across different stress conditions?

94 By clarifying these aspects, this study facilitates the understanding of dislocation-precipitate interactions
95 and macroscopic creep resistance, providing a basis for the microstructural design of advanced high-
96 temperature alloys.

2. Materials and Experimental Methodology

97 The TMT-8Cr-10Al alloy was fabricated by repetitive arc melting under argon atmosphere using an
98 AM/0.5 arc melter (Edmund Bühler GmbH, Germany). High-purity elemental constituents Ta (99.9%),
99 Mo (99.95%), Ti (99.8%), Cr (99.99%), and Al (99.99%) were supplied by chemPUR GmbH
100 (Germany). Approximately 120 g of alloy was produced through five consecutive melting and flipping
101 cycles to ensure chemical homogeneity. To eliminate the dendritic microstructure, the as-cast alloy was
102 encapsulated in Ta foil and homogenized at 1600 °C for 20 h under a constant flow of high-purity Ar.
103 Heating and cooling were controlled at 100 K/h in a HTRH 70-600/18 resistance furnace (Carbolite
104 Gero GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). The chemical composition and density of the alloy used in this work
105 were reported in a previous study [31].

106 For microstructural investigations, cuboidal specimens of size (5 × 3 × 3) mm³ prepared by electrical
107 discharge machining (EDM) were successively ground with SiC abrasive papers up to P4000 grit and
108 subsequently polished using 3 and 1 μm diamond suspensions, each for approximately 5 min. Afterward,
109 the specimens were polished for 10 min using a colloidal oxide suspension (Buehler ITW, Germany).
110 Final surface preparation was achieved through long-duration vibratory chemo-mechanical polishing
111 with a non-crystallizing oxide suspension (Struers, Germany) for a minimum of 16 h. Microstructural
112 characterization was performed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in backscattered electron
113 (BSE) mode on a Zeiss LEO 1530 operated at 20 kV. Crystallographic orientation, local strain, and
114 residual stress distributions were analyzed using electron backscatter diffraction (SEM-EBSD) with an
115 EDAX Digiview detector mounted on a Zeiss Auriga 60 SEM.

116 Compression creep specimens with dimensions of (5 × 3 × 3) mm³ were also prepared by EDM and
117 subsequently ground with SiC abrasive papers up to P2500 grit to remove any oxide and EDM surface
118 layers. Care was taken to ensure that the top and bottom faces of each specimen were strictly parallel to
119 guarantee uniform stress distribution during testing. Compression creep tests were then performed under
120 vacuum (5 × 10⁻⁵ mbar) using a Z100 electro-mechanical testing system (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG,
121 Germany) equipped with a Maytec high-temperature vacuum furnace. Specimens were tested at 1030
122 °C under applied true stresses ranging from 100 to 150 MPa. Prior to loading, each specimen was held
123 at the target temperature for 30 min under a 50 N preload to ensure uniform temperature distribution
124 and thermal stability, while maintaining a constant loading rate of 30 MPa/min. After deformation, the
125 specimens were furnace-cooled to room temperature and subsequently prepared for microstructural
126 characterization following the metallographic procedures described above. To ensure reproducibility, a
127 minimum of three independent creep tests were performed for each stress condition. For quantitative
128 analysis of the creep behavior, the minimum (or steady-state, if present) creep rate is commonly
129 expressed by the classical power-law creep equation [50]:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{\min} = A \sigma^n \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

130 where $\dot{\epsilon}_{\min}$ is the minimum creep rate, σ is the applied stress, n is the apparent stress exponent
131 reflecting the sensitivity of creep rate to stress, Q is the apparent activation energy, R is the universal
132 gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature. The parameter A is a material constant that depends on
133 factors such as elastic modulus, diffusion coefficient, and dislocation density. For the present alloy
134 system, our previous study demonstrated that under the investigated conditions (100-150 MPa, 1030 °C),
135 the creep behavior attains a steady-state regime [31]. This steady-state creep rate was therefore

136 designated as the minimum creep rate, as it represented the lowest strain rate observed during the creep
137 experiment.

138 To directly visualise the three-dimensional morphology of the B2 precipitates, a creep sample with a
139 representative grain orientation was selected. In particular, a grain oriented close to $\langle 100 \rangle$ was chosen,
140 as this orientation has previously been reported to exhibit N-type rafting behavior under creep conditions
141 [31]. Focused ion beam (FIB) milling was employed to cut a site-specific micropillar from such a grain
142 using a Thermo Fisher Helios G4-dual beam system. The micropillar was oriented to expose the top,
143 lateral, and front surfaces of the same grain, allowing a comprehensive assessment of precipitate
144 morphology along different crystallographic directions. During FIB preparation, a protective Pt layer
145 ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ thick) was first deposited to prevent ion-induced damage. Subsequent coarse milling was carried
146 out at 30 kV with a beam current of 21 nA, followed by a final polishing step using a current of 2.4 nA
147 to minimize surface artefacts. All micrographs were recorded using an in-column BSE detector, while
148 operating in immersion mode. 3D reconstruction of the precipitate network was then achieved by
149 correlating the microstructural features observed on the top, lateral, and front surfaces, providing spatial
150 information on the rafting morphology and its connectivity within the A2-B2 microstructure.

151 Crept samples underwent EBSD analysis using a Thermo Fisher Scientific Helios G4-UX SEM
152 equipped with an EDAX detector. Standard SEM-EBSD maps were acquired at an accelerating voltage
153 of 30 kV, a probe current of 13 nA, with a step size of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, which sets the spatial resolution of these
154 scans.

155 TEM lamellae were prepared from crept specimens (1030 °C for 100, 125, and 150 MPa) using the same
156 site-specific FIB approach, with lift-outs taken from the grains close to $\langle 001 \rangle$ orientation, as identified
157 from SEM-EBSD maps. The milling parameters were adjusted for foil preparation (30 kV bulk milling,
158 final cleaning at 2 kV/27 pA). Subsequent diffraction-contrast imaging was conducted using a Thermo
159 Fisher Tecnai F30 TEM operated at 300 kV. Selected area diffraction patterns (TEM-SADPs) and dark-
160 field (TEM-DF) imaging were used to identify and characterize the precipitates, while two-beam bright-
161 field (TEM-BF) imaging enabled the visualization of dislocations and their interactions with these
162 precipitates. High-resolution scanning TEM (STEM) investigations were performed in a probe-
163 corrected Titan Themis (300 kV) using a high-angle annular dark-field (STEM-HAADF) detector.
164 Atomic-resolution STEM-HAADF micrographs were acquired with a camera length of 160 mm, and
165 image drift during acquisition was compensated by using the drift-corrected frame integration function
166 in Velox software.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Composition and Initial Microstructure

167 The nominal composition of TMT-8Cr-10Al is shown in Table 1. The experimentally determined
168 concentrations, measured by SEM-EDS, deviate only slightly from the target values, confirming that
169 the alloy was produced close to its designed composition [13]. The O and N contents are within the
170 range typically reported for refractory high-entropy alloys [13,51,52]. The experimental density of this
171 alloy measured by the Archimedes method is $9.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ [31].

Table 1. Target and experimental composition (at.%) and impurity levels (wt.-ppm) of the investigated alloy [31].

	Ta	Mo	Ti	Cr	Al	O	N
	at.%					wt.-ppm	
Target	27.3	27.3	27.3	8	10	-	-
Experimental	26.0	29.8	27.4	7.3	9.4	352 ± 88	45 ± 14

172 Fig. 1 presents the initial homogenized microstructure of the alloy. Fig. 1a shows the kernel average
 173 misorientation (KAM) map, which helps visualize the local variations in crystallographic orientation
 174 and highlights regions of high density of geometrically necessary dislocations within grains. It is evident
 175 from Fig. 1a that the homogenized and furnace-cooled microstructure exhibits relatively low local
 176 misorientation, as the map predominantly shows low KAM values (i.e., blue color). The inverse pole
 177 figure map (Supplementary Fig. S1) confirms a random grain orientation distribution, indicating the
 178 absence of crystallographic texture. The average grain size is approximately $(620 \pm 180) \mu\text{m}$, which is
 179 considered sufficiently coarse, such that grain-boundary sliding does not make a significant contribution
 180 to creep deformation [31]. Fig. 1(b) shows the grain boundary character map overlaid with the image
 181 quality (IQ) map of the same region as shown in Fig. 1(a). Although most of the grain boundaries
 182 observed in Fig. 1b are high-angle grain boundaries with misorientation $> 15^\circ$, there are a few low-angle
 183 grain boundaries ($8\text{-}12^\circ$) that remain even after the homogenization heat treatment. At higher
 184 magnification, the SEM-BSE micrograph obtained from within a grain in Fig. 1(c) shows dark-contrast
 185 precipitates clearly distinguished from the bright matrix. Based on earlier diffraction and chemical
 186 analyses [12,31], the bright regions corresponds to a disordered A2 matrix phase enriched in Ta and Mo,
 187 whereas the dark regions are identified as ordered B2 precipitates, enriched in Al and Ti, with Cr being
 188 homogeneously distributed. The B2 precipitates, formed through a precipitation reaction, are uniformly
 189 distributed with an average size in the range of 10 to 20 nm with a volume fraction of around
 190 20% [12,13]. The observed two-phase microstructure establishes the baseline for the subsequent creep
 191 experiments.

Figure 1. Initial meso- and microstructure of the homogenized and furnace-cooled material. (a) KAM map; (b) grain boundary character map overlaid with IQ map from the same region; and (c) high-magnification SEM-BSE micrograph revealing A2 matrix (bright contrast) and B2 precipitates (dark contrast).

3.2 Creep Behavior

192 Fig. 2(a) presents the double-logarithmic plot of minimum creep rate versus applied stress at 1030 °C,
193 obtained from creep tests conducted at stresses between 75 and 175 MPa. A critical observation is that
194 the apparent stress exponent changes at 125 MPa. In the lower-stress regime (75 to 125 MPa), the
195 apparent stress exponent is ~ 4.3 , comparable to values reported for a dislocation climb-controlled
196 regime [53]. This suggests that dislocation climb is likely to be the dominant mechanism in the present
197 alloy, an aspect further examined in the following TEM analysis. In the higher-stress regime (125 to
198 175 MPa), however, the data deviate strongly from the low-stress trend, yielding an apparent exponent
199 of ~ 19 . Such an unusually high value indicates a breakdown of the classical power-law regime, implying
200 that additional mechanisms, such as dislocation cutting of precipitates, Orowan bypassing, cross-slip, or
201 microstructural instabilities, may become operative.

202 Based on the distinct stress-dependent creep behavior described above, three representative specimens
203 tested at 100, 125, and 150 MPa were selected for detailed microstructural characterisation and
204 investigation of the deformation mechanism. Fig. 2(b) shows the corresponding creep strain rate versus
205 creep strain curves. Based on the evolution of the creep strain rate, the specimen tested at 100 MPa
206 remains in the primary creep regime and is likely approaching the onset of the steady-state creep stage,
207 whereas the samples tested at 125 MPa and 150 MPa are well into the steady-state creep stage w.

Figure 2. Compilation of relevant creep data. (a) double-logarithmic plot of minimum creep rate versus applied stress between 75 and 175 MPa at 1030 °C, with each symbol representing the result of an individual creep sample; and (b) creep rate versus creep strain of selected specimens tested at 100, 125, and 150 MPa.

3.3 Crept Microstructure

208 Fig. 3(a-c) shows SEM-BSE micrographs of TMT-8Cr-10Al crept at 1030 °C under applied stresses of
209 100, 125, and 150 MPa, respectively. The compression axis in the micrographs is oriented horizontally.
210 Compared with the initial microstructure, where the B2 precipitates exhibit a nearly spherical
211 morphology with random spatial distribution, the crept samples show pronounced coarsening and
212 directional alignment of the precipitates (i.e., rafting). The grains shown in these micrographs are close
213 to $\langle 100 \rangle$ crystallographic directions parallel to the compression axis. As demonstrated in our previous
214 study, only grains with this specific orientation develop B2 rafts aligned perpendicular to the loading
215 axis in the polycrystalline alloy [31]. Considering the strong orientation dependence of the deformation
216 behavior, the present analysis focuses on $\langle 100 \rangle$ -oriented grains to elucidate the underlying deformation
217 mechanisms.

Figure 3. SEM-BSE micrographs of TMT-8Cr-10Al creep tested at 1030 °C under different applied stresses (a) 100 MPa, $\epsilon \approx 0.65\%$, $t \approx 183$ h; (b) 125 MPa, $\epsilon \approx 3.1\%$, $t \approx 600$ h; and (c) 150 MPa, $\epsilon \approx 4.6\%$, $t \approx 139$ h.

218 While the SEM-BSE observations provide valuable insights into the post-creep morphology of the B2
 219 precipitates, they represent only 2D projections of the underlying 3D microstructure. To visualize the
 220 morphology of the rafted precipitates, a sample that was crept at 1030 °C under 150 MPa and reached a
 221 total strain of 7.8% was selected, as it provided a sufficiently long rafted precipitate for analysis. The
 222 selected $\langle 100 \rangle$ grain orientation was identified by SEM-EBSD, as shown in Fig. 4(a). A site-specific
 223 FIB cross-sectioning was then performed on this grain, as shown in Fig. 4(b), and a micropillar was
 224 fabricated for microstructural analysis. To enable 3D reconstruction of the precipitate morphology, in-
 225 column detector (ICD) micrographs were acquired from three orthogonal views of the micropillar (top,
 226 lateral, and front faces), as illustrated in Fig. 4(c-e). Based on these perspectives, a schematic 3D model
 227 of the B2 precipitate morphology was generated in Fig. 4(f), yielding a 3D representation of the rafted
 228 precipitate arrangement in the $\langle 100 \rangle$ -oriented grain under current creep conditions. The reconstructed
 229 3D morphology reveals that the B2 precipitates adopt a plate-like geometry aligned perpendicular to the
 230 loading direction. On the top and lateral face, the precipitates appear as elongated plates, while the front
 231 faces display near-circular cross-sections, respectively, indicating that the plates are continuous and
 232 laterally interconnected. Furthermore, the apparent cut-through features marked by red arrows in
 233 Fig. 4(e) are the left-out gaps between the growing and rafted B2 precipitates, which are about to join.

Figure 4. (a) EBSD IPF map of the specimen crept at 1030 °C and 150 MPa; (b) site-specific FIB cross-section and micropillar preparation from the selected $\langle 100 \rangle$ grain, ICD micrographs of the micropillar acquired from three orthogonal views; (c) top surface; (d) lateral face; (e) front face; and (f) Schematic 3D reconstruction of the B2 precipitate morphology.

234 To examine the deformation behavior at the micrometer scale, SEM-EBSD analyses maintaining the
 235 same step size were performed on the crept samples whose corresponding creep curves are presented in
 236 Fig. 2. Fig. 5(a–c) displays the KAM maps for the three creep conditions. Compared with the
 237 homogenized condition (Fig. 2), all crept samples exhibit enhanced local misorientation resulting from
 238 creep deformation. Additionally, the strain gradient becomes increasingly pronounced as the creep stress
 239 and the total creep strain increase. The strain field can be observed to be higher near the grain boundaries
 240 of these deformed specimens. To determine whether the creep specimen has developed subgrains due
 241 to dislocation activity [54], grain boundary character maps were overlaid with IQ maps of a selected
 242 smaller region taken from Fig. 5(a–c). These maps are shown in Fig. 5(d–f). In addition to high-angle
 243 grain boundaries (HAGBs), low-angle grain boundaries (LAGBs) with misorientations in the range of
 244 $8\text{--}12^\circ$ are also observed in the homogenized specimen and persist under all three creep conditions.
 245 However, beyond these LAGBs, the IQ maps in Fig. 5(d–f) reveal clear evidence of smaller subgrains
 246 forming within the pre-existing grains in all creep conditions. It must be noted that due to limitations of
 247 the low misorientation angles and step sizes used, the precise fraction of the individual type of grain
 248 boundaries is difficult to quantify. To quantify the misorientation across these subgrain boundaries
 249 (SGBs), point-to-origin misorientation profiles were generated across the SGBs, as indicated by the
 250 dotted black lines in Fig. 5(d–f). The misorientations measured across these SGBs range from $0.6\text{--}1.2^\circ$,
 251 which is significantly lower than the $8\text{--}12^\circ$ misorientation of the pre-existing LAGBs. Given that these
 252 SGBs are absent in the homogenized and furnace-cooled condition as well as considering very small
 253 misorientation angles, their formation can be attributed to dynamic recovery during steady-state creep,
 254 which occurs through the rearrangement of dislocations to minimize the overall strain energy. The
 255 subgrains observed in Fig. 5(d–f) exhibit average sizes exceeding $50\text{--}100\ \mu\text{m}$. This value is also
 256 dependent on the size of the original grains in which they form. A detailed description of the point-to-
 257 origin misorientation maps is provided in the Supplementary Material (Fig. S2).

Figure 5. EBSD maps of TMT-8Cr-10Al after creep at 1030 °C. (a-c) KAM map showing enhanced local misorientation for samples crept at 100, 125, and 150 MPa, respectively; and (d-f) grain boundary character map overlaid with IQ map of a smaller region (highlighted by a yellow box in a-c), indicating LAGBs (yellow) and HAGBs (red). Black dotted lines are drawn across the subgrain boundaries (SGBs) formed during creep deformation.

3.4 Stress-Dependent Creep Mechanisms

258 To directly relate the observed stress-dependent creep behavior to the underlying deformation
 259 mechanisms, TEM was carried out on specimens crept under different stress levels. The analyses
 260 focused on grains oriented with $\langle 001 \rangle$ almost parallel to the compression axis, where pronounced N-
 261 type rafting was observed.

3.4.1 Low-Stress Regime

262 The specimen crept at 1030 °C and 100 MPa, which falls within the low-stress regime, exhibits an
 263 apparent stress exponent of $n \approx 4.3$. Fig. 6(a) shows the TEM-SADP acquired along the $[001]$ zone
 264 axis, displaying weak B2 superlattice spots alongside the fundamental A2/B2 spots. The corresponding
 265 TEM-DF micrograph in Fig. 6(b), obtained using a B2 superlattice spot, reveals the B2 precipitates in
 266 bright contrast against the darker A2 matrix. Compared to the undeformed condition (Fig. 1(b)), the B2
 267 precipitates are elongated and rafted along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction, consistent with the orientation
 268 relationship $\langle 001 \rangle_{B2} \parallel \langle 001 \rangle_{A2}, \{001\}_{B2} \parallel \{001\}_{A2}$ as previously reported for this alloy [31].

269 A low-magnification, two-beam TEM-BF micrograph in Fig. 6(c) provides an overview of the deformed
 270 microstructure. Under the two-beam diffraction condition, dislocations appear as dark lines, while
 271 precipitates exhibit a weak bright contrast because the imaging conditions differ from those optimized
 272 for superlattice contrast. Qualitatively, the overall dislocation density is low, consistent with the limited
 273 creep strain ($\sim 0.65\%$). Another TEM-BF micrograph, shown in Fig. 6d, reveals a curved dislocation
 274 segment that appears bypassing a B2 precipitate (indicated by the black arrow). Since the cutting of
 275 ordered precipitates requires the coordinated motion of paired dislocations [55] (see next section), this

276 configuration indicates that dislocations bypass B2 precipitates by climb [56–58], a mechanism also
 277 reported in B2-strengthened ferritic alloys [59–63]. This aligns with the measured stress exponent of n
 278 ≈ 4.3 , characteristic of climb-controlled creep [64,65].

Figure 6. TEM results of the sample crept in the low stress regime (1030 °C, 100 MPa). (a) TEM-SADP along the [001] zone axis showing the fundamental A2/B2 reflections and weak B2 superlattice spots; (b) TEM-DF-DF micrograph obtained using $\vec{g} = [100]$ B2 superlattice reflection, highlighting the B2 precipitates; (c) low-magnification two-beam TEM-BF-BF micrograph providing an overview of the crept microstructure; and (d) a relatively high-magnification two-beam TEM-BF micrograph showing a curved segment of dislocation (black arrow) bypassing a B2 precipitate via the climb mechanism.

3.4.2 Transition Regime

279 To elucidate how the active deformation mechanisms evolve with increasing stress, detailed TEM
 280 analysis was performed on the specimen crept at 1030 °C under the intermediate stress of 125 MPa. The
 281 [001] TEM-SADP in Fig. 7(a) displays the fundamental A2/B2 reflections along with B2 superlattice
 282 spots. The corresponding TEM-DF micrograph in Fig. 7(b), obtained using the $\vec{g} = [100]$ B2
 283 superlattice reflection highlights elongated B2 precipitates in bright contrast, rafted along the <100>

284 direction. The low-magnification two-beam TEM-BF image in Fig. 7(c) offers an overview of the crept
285 microstructure, revealing a more uniform distribution of dislocations and a moderate increase in their
286 density relative to the lower-stress condition.

287 A higher-magnification TEM-BF micrograph in Fig. 7(d) reveals how dislocations interact with the B2
288 precipitates. As in the 100 MPa sample, a dislocation bypassing two adjacent precipitates via climb is
289 evident. The jog segments formed as the dislocation moves around the precipitates (indicated by the
290 black arrow), revealed under the reversed diffraction condition ($-g$) in Fig. 7(e), confirm that the bypass
291 occurs through climb. The noticeable curvature of the dislocation within the A2 channel (Fig. 7d and
292 7e) further indicates that climb-assisted bypass over the B2 precipitates is slower than glide within the
293 A2 matrix.

294 However, unlike the lower-stress case, paired dislocations are frequently observed extending from the
295 matrix into the precipitates (Fig. 7(d-f)). To determine whether these paired dislocations are dipoles (i.e.,
296 a pair of dislocations moving on parallel slip planes in opposite directions) or a set of dislocations with
297 identical Burgers vectors on the same plane, the same region was imaged using the reversed diffraction
298 vector ($-g$), as shown in Fig. 7(e). The spacing and contrast of paired dislocations within the A2 matrix
299 remain unchanged upon g -reversal, confirming that they lie on the same slip plane and are not dipoles.
300 However, the paired segments inside the B2 precipitates reverse contrast (highlighted by dashed ellipses
301 in Fig. 7(d) and 7(e)), demonstrating that they are superpartials with identical Burgers vectors gliding
302 on the same slip plane within the ordered B2 phase. One dislocation in each pair exhibits noticeably
303 weaker contrast in Fig. 7(d), and its contrast reverses under g -reversal in Fig. 7(e), likely due to elastic
304 interactions between the paired segments [66,67]. These observations confirm that the dislocations
305 within B2 are superpartials cutting through the ordered precipitates via coordinated motion. Additional
306 instances of paired dislocations near precipitates, likely corresponding to earlier or forthcoming cutting
307 events [68], are visible in Fig. 7(f).

308 Because the 125 MPa condition falls within the transition between the low-stress climb-controlled
309 regime ($n \approx 4.3$) and the high-stress regime ($n \approx 19$), the concurrent operation of dislocation climb
310 (diffusion-assisted) and superpartial-mediated precipitate cutting (glide-controlled) is consistent with
311 the expected coexistence of multiple deformation mechanisms in this intermediate region [69,70].
312 Additionally, long dislocation segments within A2 channels are observed in Fig. 7(g), and trace analysis
313 indicates that they are gliding on (110) or (112) planes. Occasional dislocation dipoles are also observed,
314 confirmed by g -reversal in Fig. 7(h) and 7(i).

Figure 7. TEM results of the sample crept in the transition regime (1030 °C, 125 MPa). (a) TEM-SADP along the [001] zone axis (ZA) showcasing the fundamental A2/B2 reflections and weak B2 superlattice spots; (b) TEM-DF micrograph taken using $\vec{g} = [100]$ B2 superlattice reflection; (c) a low-magnification two-beam TEM-BF micrograph taken along [113] ZA presents the overview of the deformed microstructure; (d) two-beam TEM-BF micrograph showing dislocation climb (pink arrows) and superpartial-mediated cutting of a B2 precipitate (ellipse); (e) same area as 'd' imaged under a reversed diffraction vector ($-\vec{g}$), revealing the jogged climb segment (black arrow) and contrast reversal of superpartials within B2; (f) paired dislocations (yellow arrow) near precipitates, indicative of earlier or forthcoming cutting events; (g) long dislocation segments within A2 channels (red arrow), with corresponding trace analysis marked by solid lines; (h) and (i) two-beam BF micrographs taken under $\pm \vec{g}$, confirming the presence of dislocation dipoles.

3.4.3 High-Stress Regime

315 The specimen crept at 1030 °C under 150 MPa lies in the high-stress regime, where the apparent stress
 316 exponent increases to ~ 19 . As in the low- and intermediate-stress conditions (100 and 125 MPa), the B2
 317 precipitates remain rafted along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ direction (Fig. 8(a) and 8(b)).

318 The low-magnification two-beam TEM-BF micrograph in Fig. 8(c) provides an overview of the
 319 deformed microstructure, showcasing long dislocations within the A2 channels. Many of these

320 dislocations exhibit abrupt directional changes, forming step-like features (indicated by yellow arrows).
 321 A detailed trace analysis (solid lines in Fig. 8(d)) confirms that these dislocations undergo multiple
 322 cross-slip among $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ planes. Imaging the same dislocation along the $[113]$ zone axis (Fig.
 323 8(e)) reveals a similar overall geometry, without any change in curvature, but with apparent differences
 324 in the lengths of individual segments, further substantiating cross-slip activity.

325 Additionally, a TEM-BF micrograph acquired along the $[113]$ zone axis (Fig. 8(f)) also shows multiple
 326 dislocation–precipitate interactions, including climb bypass (indicated by blue arrows). Notably, no
 327 evidence of B2 precipitate cutting by dislocations is observed in any of the TEM micrographs.

Figure 6. TEM results of the sample crept in the high stress regime (1030 °C, 150 MPa). (a) TEM-SADP along the $[001]$ zone axis (ZA) showcasing the fundamental A2/B2 reflections and weak B2 superlattice spots; (b) TEM-DF micrograph taken using $\vec{g} = [100]$ B2 superlattice reflection; (c) a low-magnification two-beam TEM-BF micrograph showcasing the overview of the deformed microstructure with long dislocation segments in A2 channels, many displaying step-like features (yellow arrows); (d,e) a representative dislocation imaged along the $[001]$ and $[113]$ zone axes, with trace analysis shown in (d) confirming multiple cross-slip events; and (f) TEM-BF micrograph along the $[113]$ zone axis illustrating various dislocation–precipitate interactions, including climb bypass (blue arrows).

3.4.4 Nature of the A2/B2 Interface after Creep

328 The stability of the matrix–precipitate interface is crucial to the creep behavior of precipitation-
 329 strengthened alloys. To investigate the nature and coherency of the precipitate–matrix interface, high-
 330 resolution STEM-HAADF experiments were performed on the specimen crept at 1030 °C and 125 MPa.
 331 Micrographs were acquired along the $[001]$ zone axis from different interface locations marked in Fig.
 332 9(a). Fig. 9(b₁), (c₁), and (d₁) show the atomic-resolution images of these interface sections, while
 333 Fig. 9(b₂), (c₂), and (d₂) present the corresponding inverse FFT images obtained using masked
 334 $(110)_{A2, B2}$ spots from the FFT patterns, see Fig. 9(b₃). The continuity of the (110) planes across
 335 multiple interface regions confirms that the interfaces remain coherent, demonstrating the stability of
 336 the B2–A2 interface even after rafting under these creep conditions. This observation is consistent with

337 the coherency seen in the 150 MPa crept sample (not shown) and aligns with previous reports on
 338 undeformed specimens annealed for up to 1000 hours [49], underscoring the inherent stability of the
 339 A2/B2 interface across diverse conditions.

Figure 7. Nature of the interface between the A2 matrix and B2 precipitates in the specimen crept at 1030 °C under 125 MPa up to a strain of 3.1%. (a) Low-magnification HAADF-STEM micrograph showing an elongated, rafted B2 precipitate within the A2 matrix; (b₁, c₁ and d₁) high-resolution HAADF-STEM micrographs of different sections of the precipitate–matrix interface, as indicated in (a); (b₂, c₂ and d₂) Corresponding inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) images obtained using the (110) spots from the FFT patterns. One representative FFT pattern corresponding to Figure (b₁) is shown in Figure (b₃).

3.4.5 Deformation Mechanisms

340 The test conducted at 1030 °C and 100 MPa (low-stress regime) was interrupted before the onset of
 341 secondary creep. The resulting microstructure (Fig. 6) exhibits a low dislocation density and well-
 342 developed {100}-rafted B2 precipitates, with occasional climb events (Fig. 6d) enabling dislocations to
 343 bypass the precipitates. No evidence of B2 precipitate cutting is observed at this stress level, indicating
 344 that dislocation climb is the dominant creep mechanism. This is consistent with the relatively low
 345 apparent stress exponent (~4.3), characteristic of climb-controlled deformation.

346 At 125 MPa (transition regime), the specimen exhibits a prolonged steady-state creep regime
 347 accompanied by markedly increased dislocation activity. While dislocation climb remains operative, an
 348 additional mechanism emerges: cutting of B2 precipitates by paired dislocations (Fig. 7d and e). These
 349 paired segments correspond to strongly coupled superpartials cutting the ordered B2 phase in a
 350 coordinated manner, consistent with behavior previously reported under room-temperature deformation
 351 [49]. This suggested that the higher creep stress facilitates the coordinated motion of two dislocations,
 352 enabling them to cut the B2 precipitates. The microstructure also contains dipoles and several long
 353 dislocations on {110} or {112} planes within the A2 channels (Fig. 7g), likely possessing a major screw
 354 character, as commonly observed in BCC alloys [71–74]. Thus, the transition regime is governed by a
 355 combination of B2 cutting by coupled dislocations and climb-assisted bypass, although the relative
 356 contributions of these mechanisms cannot be quantified.

357 At 150 MPa (high-stress regime), the creep response ($n \approx 19$) appears to be governed by extensive cross-
 358 slip of screw dislocations between the {110} and {112} planes (Fig. 8c–d), producing the characteristic
 359 step-like features along the dislocation lines. Some climb events are still observed (Fig. 8f), but they are

360 comparatively rare. Notably, no evidence of B2 precipitate cutting is found at this stress level, indicating
361 a shift toward creep dominated by repeated cross-slip.

362 Across all stress conditions, the B2 precipitates exhibit consistent $\langle 100 \rangle$ rafting. As rafting progresses,
363 the A2 channels narrow and the spacing between adjacent B2 precipitates decreases due to coalescence
364 (Fig. 6b). This evolving morphology considerably raises the critical Orowan stress required for
365 dislocations to bow out between precipitates [75], making Orowan looping highly improbable
366 throughout the entire stress range. The absence of Orowan loops in all TEM observations reinforces this
367 conclusion.

368 Within this rafting framework, the high-stress specimen shows a distinct microstructural feature: the
369 rafted B2 structure at 150 MPa (Fig. 8b) is finer along the rafting direction compared to low-stress (Fig.
370 6b) and transition-regime samples (Fig. 7b). All micrographs were acquired along the [001] zone axis
371 at comparable magnifications, making this comparison reliable. Because dislocations predominantly
372 reside within the A2 channels, the relatively larger channel spacing in the high-stress sample allows
373 greater freedom for dislocation motion between adjacent channels.

374 Under these conditions, two mechanisms could, in principle, accommodate dislocation motion: Orowan
375 looping or cross slip. However, the high Orowan stress associated with the rafted morphology renders
376 cross slip energetically more favourable [76]. TEM micrographs (Fig. 8c–d) confirm frequent cross slip
377 of screw dislocations between $\{110\}$ and $\{112\}$ planes, indicating that creep at 150 MPa is dominated
378 by cross-slip-mediated glide. This behavior aligns with the broader understanding that thermally
379 activated glide governs creep in the power-law breakdown regime of crystalline materials [64,77].
380 Nonetheless, due to the limited field of view in TEM, additional deformation pathways on larger scales
381 cannot be entirely ruled out.

382 As the creep properties are comparable, or even superior, to some of the state-of-the-art Ni-based
383 superalloys [31], it is essential to compare the dislocation activity as well. Unlike precipitation-
384 strengthened Ni-based superalloys, which commonly develop extensive dislocation networks during
385 creep [78,79], the TMT-10Al-8Cr alloy shows no such network formation. The reason behind such
386 observation can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, Ni-based superalloys are ductile and can
387 accommodate a large amount of strain, which eventually leads to extensive dislocation-dislocation
388 interaction [80–82] assisted by octahedral slip in the A1 matrix [83–85]. In contrast, A2-B2 refractory
389 alloys are comparably brittle [24,37,76], and the tests were interrupted at a maximum strain of 5%,
390 which explains the reduced dislocation density observed in the current study. Additionally, the restricted
391 motion of jogged screw dislocations [87] prevents extensive dislocation-dislocation interaction in the
392 A2 channels. Furthermore, in Ni-based superalloys, the lattice misfit between A1 and L_{12} leads to the
393 formation of an interfacial dislocation network to accommodate the misfit strain, and their interaction
394 with slip dislocations leads to the formation of an extensive dislocation network in A1 channels
395 [6,10,11,88]. The knitting reaction and ease of L_{12} cutting control the creep process [6,10,10,88,89]. In
396 contrast, both A2 and B2 in the studied alloy maintain lattice coherency in the initial as well as during
397 the entire creep duration (see Fig. 9). Thus, an initial dislocation network formation at the beginning of
398 creep is not formed, and the subsequent network formation is suppressed by reduced dislocation density,
399 explained earlier.

4. Conclusions

400 This study builds on our previous work, which established that the TMT-8Cr-10Al alloy exhibits two
401 distinct creep regimes at 1030°C, with a critical transition occurring near 125 MPa. However, the
402 specific microstructural changes and dislocation-precipitate interactions underlying this stress-
403 dependent behavior remained unresolved. Within this context, the main contributions of the present
404 work are:

- 405 1. Three-dimensional morphology of rafted B2 precipitates: FIB-based 3D reconstruction reveals,
406 for the first time, the true spatial morphology of the rafted B2 precipitates, which form laterally
407 continuous but vertically separated plate-like structures.
- 408 2. Stress-dependent evolution of dislocation-precipitate interactions: The deformation mechanism
409 during creep transitions from a climb-controlled mechanism in the low stress regime (100 MPa)
410 to a cross-slip-controlled mechanism in the high stress regime (150 MPa). Whereas deformation
411 in the transition regime (125 MPa) is governed by a combination of climb-controlled glide and
412 cutting of B2 precipitates by strongly coupled dislocations.
- 413 3. Post-creep A2/B2 interface: High-resolution scanning TEM further confirms that the A2/B2
414 interfaces remain fully coherent across all creep conditions examined.

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Conflict of Interest

425 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

426 The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17872767> under CC BY-
427 SA 4.0 license. Further information is available upon request with sandipan.sen@kit.edu,
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